

ISic0639

I.Sicily inscription 0639

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

brick

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Centuripe

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332877

1. Λείβερτε

2. χρηστέ,

3. χάρε.

4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644881

EDCS 64800566

PHI 332877

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques*

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1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 44.0745

Manganaro, G. 1994. Iscrizioni, epigrafi ed epigrammi in Greco della Sicilia orientale di epoca romana. *Mélanges de l'École Française de Rome: Antiquité.* 106: 79-118. At 85 no.3a fig.5

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